

Kinetic method for the estimation of aldopentoses

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Abstract : Kinetic methods of analysis are now accepted as standard analytical procedure for various types of samples. Aldopentoses (D-xylose, D-arabinose and D-ribose) have been estimated in simulated samples by kinetic (uncatalyzed) method (D-xylose and D-arabinose [0.05–0.3 M] and D-ribose [0.0250–0.1375 M]) using cerium(IV)-aldopentose redox indicator reaction in sulphuric acid medium. The indicator reaction is well understood as electron transfer reaction. The investigations have been made from the calibration plots obtained by using pseudo first order rate constant data of the indicator reaction and also by fixed time and fixed concentration procedures. The rate data was obtained for the indicator reaction under varying kinetic experimental conditions. Results of this study indicate that estimated values for the simulated samples are consistent and reproducible within $\sim \pm 1\%$.

Keywords : Kinetic determination, aldopentoses, estimation, redox reaction, kinetic estimation.

Introduction

Metal ion oxidants have been widely employed in synthetic chemistry¹⁻³ including carbohydrate chemistry⁴⁻⁶. These are stable, inexpensive and can readily be stored and handled. Kinetic method of analysis have been widely developed and accepted in chemical analysis of different samples⁷⁻¹¹. The application of chemical analysis by kinetic methods can be either in homogeneous or heterogeneous system involving both catalytic and/or noncatalytic methods. The present work describes the preliminary procedure for the estimation of aldopentoses with Ce^{IV} in sulphuric acid medium^{12,13}.

Results and discussion

Indicator reaction :

The reaction followed first order kinetics up to 2 half lives. The rate increased with the first power of concentrations of aldopentoses, sulphuric acid, hydrogen ion, bisulphate ion. These indicator reactions between aldopentoses and cerium(IV) in sulphuric acid medium under the kinetic run conditions can be represented as in eq. (1),

The formation of formic acid was confirmed by usual spot test and now by paper and high performance liquid chromatography methods. The formation of intermediate carbon centered aldopentose free radicals were confirmed by induced polymerization reaction with acryl nitrile and also by the earlier reported EPR spin trapping studies¹⁴.

Kinetic estimation :

The rate of these indicator reactions under the present kinetic conditions in terms of disappearance of cerium(IV) with time at constant temperature and sulphuric acid concentration can be given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = k_0 [\text{cerium(IV)}]_0 [\text{aldopentose}]_0 = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_0 \quad (2)$$

Thus, when $[\text{aldopentose}]_0 \gg [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_0$

then,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 [\text{aldopentoses}] \quad (3)$$

Eq. (2) alternatively expressed as eq. (4) for the finite change in the initial concentration of cerium(IV) in a given fixed time interval,

$$-\frac{\Delta[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{\Delta t} = k_0 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_0 [\text{aldopentoses}]_0 \quad (4)$$

The initial concentration of cerium(IV) i.e. $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_0$ is kept constant in each kinetic run with varying initial concentration of aldopentoses i.e. $[\text{aldopentose}]_0$, therefore,

$$-\frac{\Delta[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{\Delta t} = k_0 [\text{aldopentoses}]_0 \quad (5)$$

Eqs. (3) and (5) have been used to obtain the following different three calibration plots to determine the concentrations (D-xylose and D-arabinose [0.05–0.3 M] and D-ribose [0.0250–0.1375 M]) of simulated samples of aldopentoses.

- k_{obs} and $[\text{aldopentose}]$.
- Absorbance i.e. $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_0$ and $[\text{aldopentose}]_0$ at fixed time intervals.
- Time in seconds and $[\text{aldopentose}]_0$ at fixed absorbance i.e. at fixed concentration of $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_0$.

The kinetic data of variation of k_{obs} , [Figs. 1(a), (b), (c)] absorbance at fixed time interval [Figs. 2(a), (b), (c)] and time at fixed absorbance with initial concentration of pentose [Figs. 3(a), (b), (c)] in different kinetic run are given graphically for D-xylose, D-arabinose, D-ribose.

The graphical data has been used to obtain unknown concentration of simulated samples of aldopentoses using regression equations in respective graphs. The results of the estimations with actual theoretical values are also given in respective figures.

Experimental

Materials :

Commercially available chemicals of pure quality were used without further purification. Stock solutions of aldopentoses were prepared in double distilled water. Ce^{IV} stock solutions were prepared by dissolving ceric sulphate (make : Loba Chem., potency : 99.0%) in aqueous sulphuric acid.

Kinetic method :

The kinetic runs were performed in stoppered glass vessels in a controlled temperature (± 0.1 °C) water-bath. The kinetics of redox reaction between aldopentoses (D-xylose, D-arabinose and D-ribose) and cerium(IV) in

sulphuric acid medium was followed under pseudo first order condition by measuring absorbance at 316 nm (λ_{max} for Ce^{IV} – Shimadzu 1700 model) at constant temperature. The unknown is calculated in simulated sample by fixed time method and fixed absorbance method from the regression equations.

$$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} = 5.3399 [\text{D-xylose}] - 0.5994 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.99$$

Result : 10^2 [Unknown-1] (mol dm^{-3}) = 1.57 (calcd.); 1.50 (actual)

10^2 [Unknown-2] (mol dm^{-3}) = 2.32 (calcd.); 2.25 (actual)

(a) Estimation of D-xylose

$$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} = 6.5006 [\text{D-arabinose}] + 0.1535 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.99$$

Result : 10^2 [Unknown-1] (mol dm^{-3}) = 1.58 (calcd.); 1.50 (actual)

10^2 [Unknown-2] (mol dm^{-3}) = 2.34 (calcd.); 2.25 (actual)

(b) Estimation of D-arabinose

$$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} = 2.7795 [\text{D-ribose}] + 4.6103 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.97$$

Result : 10^2 [Unknown] (mol dm^{-3}) = 8.78 (calcd.); 8.75 (actual)

(c) Estimation of D-ribose

Fig. 1. Estimation of aldopentoses by variation of k_{obs} with $[\text{aldopentose}]$. $10^4 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 2.5$ mol dm^{-3} ; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.45$ mol dm^{-3} ; Temp. = 296 K; $\lambda = 316$ nm.

$$A_6 = -0.2187 [\text{D-xylose}] + 1.3077 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.99$$

$$A_{12} = -0.2843 [\text{D-xylose}] + 1.2371 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.99$$

$$A_{18} = -0.3113 [\text{D-xylose}] + 1.1532 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.98$$

Result : 10^2 [Unknown-1] (mol dm⁻³) = 1.52 ± 0.02 (calcd.); 1.50 (actual)

10^2 [Unknown-2] (mol dm⁻³) = 2.29 ± 0.01 (calcd.); 2.25 (actual)

(a) Estimation of D-xylose

$$t_{1.1} = -16.400 [\text{D-xylose}] + 47.00 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.96$$

$$t_{0.9} = -48.234 [\text{D-xylose}] + 136.69 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.90$$

$$t_{0.7} = -60.646 [\text{D-xylose}] + 192.25 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.95$$

Result : 10^2 [Unknown-1] (mol dm⁻³) = 1.48 ± 0.03 (calcd.); 1.50 (actual)

10^2 [Unknown-2] (mol dm⁻³) = 2.22 ± 0.04 (calcd.); 2.25 (actual)

(a) Estimation of D-xylose

$$A_6 = -0.2298 [\text{D-arabinose}] + 1.2727 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.98$$

$$A_{12} = -0.2732 [\text{D-arabinose}] + 1.1574 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.97$$

$$A_{18} = -0.2898 [\text{D-arabinose}] + 1.0555 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.96$$

Result : 10^2 [Unknown-1] (mol dm⁻³) = 1.49 ± 0.04 (calcd.); 1.50 (actual)

10^2 [Unknown-2] (mol dm⁻³) = 2.28 ± 0.02 (calcd.); 2.25 (actual)

(b) Estimation of D-arabinose

$$t_{1.1} = -10.873 [\text{D-arabinose}] + 32.648 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.88$$

$$t_{0.9} = -32.287 [\text{D-arabinose}] + 97.988 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.84$$

$$t_{0.7} = -51.821 [\text{D-arabinose}] + 167.29 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.90$$

Result : 10^2 [Unknown-1] (mol dm⁻³) = 1.47 ± 0.01 (calcd.); 1.50 (actual)

10^2 [Unknown-2] (mol dm⁻³) = 2.23 ± 0.03 (calcd.); 2.25 (actual)

(b) Estimation of D-arabinose

$$A_3 = -0.0463 [\text{D-ribose}] + 1.1901 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.95$$

$$A_6 = -0.0560 [\text{D-ribose}] + 1.0237 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.91$$

$$A_9 = -0.0531 [\text{D-ribose}] + 0.8569 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.85$$

Result : 10^2 [Unknown] (mol dm⁻³) = 8.98 ± 0.06 (calcd.); 8.75 (actual)

(c) Estimation of D-ribose

$$t_{1.1} = -13.878 [\text{D-ribose}] + 193.130 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.75$$

$$t_{0.9} = -30.117 [\text{D-ribose}] + 426.940 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.71$$

$$t_{0.7} = -51.821 [\text{D-ribose}] + 676.760 \quad \text{Corr. coeff.} = 0.73$$

Result : 10^2 [Unknown] (mol dm⁻³) = 8.83 ± 0.04 (calcd.); 8.75 (actual)

(c) Estimation of D-ribose

Fig. 2. Estimation of aldopentoses by variation of absorbance at fixed time. 10^{-4} [Ce^{IV}] = 2.5 mol dm⁻³; [H₂SO₄] = 1.45 mol dm⁻³; Temp. = 296 K; λ = 316 nm.

Fig. 3. Estimation of aldopentoses by variation of time at fixed absorbance. 10^{-4} [Ce^{IV}] = 2.5 mol dm⁻³; [H₂SO₄] = 1.45 mol dm⁻³; Temp. = 296 K; λ = 316 nm.

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